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**CRYPTOGRAPHY IN DATA PROTECTION OF BANKING INFORMATION
 SYSTEMS OF PERSONAL DATA**

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59407–2021, 117, 851- 30.01.2025 ., 01.03.2026 .), (34.12-2015 « » « »)

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The article provides a comprehensive analysis of modern cryptographic methods of personal data protection in banking personal data information systems (ISPs), taking into account the current requirements of the legislation of the Russian Federation and regulatory documents for November 2025. The relevance of the study is due to the tightening of the requirements of the Bank of Russia and the FSB for personal data protection in the context of digitalization of banking services and the growth of cyber threats, as well as the need to switch to domestic cryptographic standards as part of the import substitution policy. The work uses a systematic approach that includes an analysis of the regulatory framework (GOST R 59407-2021, Regulation of the Bank of Russia No. 851-P dated 01/30/2025, as well as prospective provisions of the FSTEC of Russia Order No. 117, effective 03/01/2026), classification of personal data security threats, evaluation of the effectiveness of modern cryptographic algorithms (GOST R 34.12-2015 «Kuznechik», «Magma») and means of cryptographic information protection (CryptoPro EDS). Based on the conducted research, a set of practical recommendations has been developed for building cryptographic protection of bank ISPs, ensuring compliance with the requirements of FZ-152 and regulatory enactments. The practical significance of the work lies in the development of recommendations for the effective implementation of cryptographic protection measures, optimization of key management processes and integration of the ICI with the existing banking infrastructure. The research results can be used by information security specialists of banking organizations to build and improve personal data protection systems, as well as to develop training programs in the field of information security in the financial sector.

Keywords: cryptography, banking information systems for personal data, personal data, GOST R 34.12-2015, cryptographic information protection tools, CryptoPro, Federal Law No. 152, Bank of Russia, Federal Security Service (FSB), key management, cryptographic protection, information security, certified security tools.

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